

A brief study on Technological advancement in Advertising industry in India

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Abstract

The technology has been a proven dynamic stream to the advertising world today. The technology is rapidly bringing the inventions to the business world. People now, are analyzing, understanding and appreciating the products and services. The major role is played by the communications of companies to the market and customers. Promotional strategies of the companies are more customer-centric now. This paper attempts to seek the technological advancements, their benefits and opportunities to the advertising industry in India. The advertising industry is heading towards virtual world from the older brick and mortar system.

Key Words: Technology, Advertising, Technological advancement, Advertising industry.

Introduction:

Today there is demand of upgraded technology from the market and every area of business is getting affected by it. The companies are busy in providing the best services to their customers by way of using every possible technology they can use. Marketing and Advertising is no exception for it. Tapp and Hughes (2004) have opined the importance of use of IT in marketing field today. Their study discusses about the high requirements of skills set from manager to be utilized in marketing department in a firm. The new technology has significance impact on marketing activities and on the role of marketers.¹ It is being observed since last few years that there is increase in number of mobile internet users in India. An internet user spends nearly 71% of internet time using his mobile device. Hence the mobile phone is considered as a key weapon for instant gratification.² To cater the need of such mobile user the advertising industry is continuously improving by bringing up innovations and new adaptations in technology. The advertising industry uses the Artificial Intelligence and data analytics with a full swing to cater the expectations of the people.³

It is the technology that continuously changing its forms in the business today and is more creative than its previous version. The technology helps business to grow, prosper, create relationships and strengthen the effective functioning of organization. The technologies such as mobile phones, internet, social media, and customer relationship management systems affect strongly on the way the companies want to communicate, deliver the message and establish a positive relationship with the customer.⁴

Research Objectives:

1. To explain the various technological advancements in ad Industry in India
2. To study the trends in advertising that seek benefits to marketers to reach customers
3. To observe the importance of technology and its usage in the field of advertising and marketing

Research Methodology:

The research is based on the developments of technology used by advertising firms in India. Hence the data has been collected from the firms, websites of government organization, published journals and news articles. The data is based on various authentic sources of publications. The researcher used the secondary data.

Some Latest technologies used in advertising industry:

Digital technology allowed companies to have online and offline interactions with the customers in the manner they want in India.⁵

Analytical tools available using internet:

Google analytics, Adobe analytics

Conversion Optimization and its tools:

It is a practice of getting people do what the companies want them to do as far as possible when they visit the company's website. Survey shows that a 3% of people visiting the company's website watch online advertising and fill up the response forms. This ensures companies at least to record the email id of visitor. If company wants to optimize the conversion, it requires increasing the conversion rating. Few of tools that are offered by various firms such as Landing Page Grader offered by 'Wordstream', A/B test run on landing pages by 'Optimizely', creating and testing A/B page landing by 'Unbounce', tools for non-programmers to create marketing apps provided by 'Ion Interactive'.⁶

Some other tools used for Conversion Rate Optimization are classified in Qualitative tools, Quantitative tools, Testing and Measuring tools. The quantitative tools allow to gather the numerical data and track the record. These tools are General Analytical tools, Website Heat Map Tools, Funnel tools, Customer satisfaction tools (CSAT), Form analysis tools and Net Promoter system. Qualitative tools help to understand the questions such as why things happen. These include Website Feedback tools, Session recording and replay tools, usability tools, Usability testing tools.⁷

Email:

Emails are used not only to communicate about product to customer directly, but also help the companies to get permission from the people to receive the additional information of company and product on their request.⁸ Some of the leading tools used in emailing are- Mailchimp email, campaigning, Constant contact.

Marketing Automation Programme:

It is the combined technology that includes personalizing websites content, tracking people whenever they visit the company's website, providing analytics, online forms, facilitating sales and marketing, automated alerts to sales people and much more. This brings all functions of software together integrates those functions. Some of the leading Marketing automation programs are provided by Hubspot, Act-on, Marketo, Oracle Eloqua, Adobe Campaign, Infusionsoft, Silverpop.⁹

Search Engine Marketing:

Search Engine Marketing involves paid search ads and Search Engine Optimization that give one the benefits of testing and optimize keywords, ad copies and offers. Search Engine Marketing has a set of activities including Social Media Marketing, Search Engine Optimization, and other search engine related functions. Some leading tools are Google AdWords, Bing and Yahoo, Wordtracker, Brightage.¹⁰

Remarketing:

It is a practice of displaying ads to appear customers on all other sites they visit one after other. More than half of Software firms use Remarketing. Some leading tools are Google AdWord remarketing, Perfect Audience from Martin Software.¹¹

Programmatic Advertising:

Programmatic advertisement is the use of software in which machines and algorithms are used to purchase the digital advertising. It is useful by various means and characterized by efficient and quick process, allowing advertisers to increase conversions and lower the customer acquisition cost.¹² In India, expenditure made on programmatic advertising was 10% against that of direct advertisement of 90% and in the year 2020 the expenditure made on programmatic advertising has grown to 38% as against to direct advertisement with 62% to expenditure contribution. The expense contribution of programmatic advertising in India is estimated to reach 42%. Looking at the overall projections of programmatic advertising, it shows the inflating trend in Indian market.¹³

But for many companies programmatic advertising is not very familiar as this technology uses many jargons. Based on geography, demography, behavioural aspects, time of day, weather and device the programmatic advertising

places the ad units. The data trustworthiness, preference of direct advertising, limited audience and high cost considerations are some of the key limitations of Programmatic advertising.¹⁴ There are more opportunities rising up for the programmatic advertising in CTV and DOOH (Digital-Out of Home) along with traditional programming channels

The programmatic buying enables the marketers and advertisers to target customers more swiftly allowing them to tailor a specific message to the right person, at right time in the right context with online adverts or DOOH.¹⁵

Chatbots:

This is a new technology that enables advertiser to get engaged with hundreds of customers at once. Chatbots is a form of Artificial Intelligence. This technology is used to answer the simple questions, attend instant inquiries and 24x7 customer services. Studies show that 63% of people prefer to use Chatbots for solving queries.¹⁶ The Chatbots are used for the service provision purpose while solving queries the thousands of customer at a certain point of time. These Chatbots generate a real time conversation with the customer and also answer the queries of the customers based on their responses.¹⁷

Real Time Bidding: (RTB)

The ROI of the traditional media like newspaper and magazines are measured in terms of their circulations, but in the era of mobiles phones that are connected to internet, it's difficult to get understood the ROI of advertising made by use of social platforms. Both the traditional and print media cannot assure that the advertisement is being viewed and generated the desired ROI. Therefore the Real Time Bidding (RTB) existed that enables the advertisers to bid advertising through the auction of advertising space and deliver the ad impression. This platform enables the advertisers to buy ads across the range. Buyer then picks one impression by using technologies such as Demand Side Platforms (DSP). This helps companies to experience a better reach and ROI.¹⁸

Conclusion:

The technological advancement in advertising industry have paved way to the marketers to bring the customers and sellers closer than ever before. The rise of internet in last century has made significant effects on commerce and business. Traditional ways of advertising are now at declining phase due to some modern and urging technological developments in advertising industry. The consumer today is using many gadgets like smartphones, laptops, smartwatches, for quick and easy access of content on internet. This provides the opportunities to the advertising firms to go for advanced technological platforms. The technologies such as automated bidding, Artificial Intelligence,

Machine Learning, Chatbots, Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality have widen the role and importance of digital advertising. The emergence of Digital Advertising is definitely setting a milestone in the advertising industry that may bring up the new trends year on year in future.

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